

Antecedents of Employee Satisfaction and its impact on Job Turnover

AUTHORS

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Abstract

Although various research, studies have been conducted to understand the concept of employee satisfaction but still organizations are unable to capture those variables that affect the employee satisfaction the most. The purpose of this study is to find out the factors that affect employee satisfaction and how much is the intensity. Specifically, we took employee empowerment, workplace environment and pay & promotion as the antecedents to see their impact on employee satisfaction and further the impact of employee satisfaction on employee turnover. A questionnaire was developed in order to collect the data for understanding the employee satisfaction level in various organizations. Convenient sampling was used to collect the data and 150 questionnaires were filled from the employees of different private and public organizations. Statistically, association of employee empowerment and workplace environment with employee satisfaction showed significant results, but the relationship between pay and promotion and employee satisfaction was somewhat insignificant. Furthermore, the effect of employee satisfaction on turnover intention of employees was also significant. This study will help the managers and organizations to better understand about the satisfaction level of employees and how they can motivate their employees to perform their job efficiently and effectively.

Key words – employee empowerment, workplace environment, pay and promotion, employee satisfaction, employee turnover.

1. Introduction:

There are certain basics in employee's behavior that need to be recognized and understood by organizations so as to further develop their employees' performance, thus utilizing all his potential to the maximum. It is a common belief that if the employer provides his employee the peace of work, reasonable wages and conducive environment, then the employee will reciprocate in the same terms and give out his best.

A successful organization strives to discover that there is a great degree of collaboration, communication, assurance, employee satisfaction and temptation levels among its staff so that they would be more incentivized towards their work responsibilities and achieving overall organizational goals. Under these circumstances, the performance level of the employee rises to amazing heights and the employer shows readiness to further enhance the facilities and fringe benefits of the employees. The contentment of the workers is an indication of the employee's satisfaction as it is a measure of sincerity and commitment of the employees with their job and working environment. Keeping spirits high among intelligent workers can be of great benefit to any company, as satisfied workers will be more likely to produce more, take fewer days off, and stay loyal to the company. There are many factors involved in improving and maintaining the employee satisfaction high, which intelligent employers would do fine to execute.

Most of the organizations in the world conduct interviews and surveys to know about the satisfaction level of employees and gain information about their working attitude. Both of these methods have fruits and flaws, so for better understanding one should select the more reliable option. On one side, there are surveys that allow the respondents to give a more clear view because they are more talkative, on the other hand, there are interviews. Interviews may have biased

results, as the employee is frightened about the consequences of saying any negative word about their organization or the supervisor.

The objective of our study is to know about the factors that affect the satisfaction level of an employee in an organization how much they affect. Specifically, we took employee empowerment, workplace environment and pay & promotion as the independent variables to see their effect on the satisfaction level of employees and further their effect on the turnover intention of employees. The area of this research is to find the satisfaction level of the employee satisfaction and helps organization to know about the factors that influence employee satisfaction.

An employee's organizational behavior is the major determinants of his job satisfaction. If an employee is satisfied with his organization or with his supervisor then he can work more devotedly and with more concentration and sincerity. Therefore, if an employee motivated and encouraged his satisfaction, level may rise; this can be done in a number of ways e.g. by giving him incentives when he achieves the required targets. Therefore, many companies conduct training programs, performance appraisal and incentive packages for the employees who have outstanding performance. These policies are different from company to company and the main target of the companies is to create loyal employees, because when the employees are faithful they will generate more for company, it is more particular in service industry, because the cordial relationship developed by the employee becomes a source of durable partnership proving beneficial for the employer. On the other side, there are retail companies, whose main priority is to satisfy employee not the employee loyalty.

As far as our view is concerned, satisfying an employee assist a company to keep the regularity in the sales and to enhance the yield by appreciating the employees. The focus

of this research study is to find the key factors that help to create the interest of the employee towards his job. Even though the study of Human Resource Management is the primary objective of any organization, therefore studying human resource helps the managers to know about the hurdles that stop an employee to work properly and what are those factors, which motivate the employees.

Studies relating to employees discover the issues that encourage employees to "go the extra mile" and through employees feel their success in the organization's success. On the other hand, employee satisfaction pay focuses at pay justice and safety of job, individual achievement, work load, balance between working hours and personal life and capacity to control organization's way, an assembling that has often been described, discussed and researched.. A contented employee is satisfied with the pay structure, promotion plan, working conditions, office timings, etc. A devoted employee is the one who has no intention to leave the organization and he works more sincerely and efficiently to achieve the targets of the organization. Hence, these employees enhance the reputation of their company through their lip service.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Employee's Satisfaction

People's belief, consideration and perception about their jobs have been related with Employee's satisfaction (Spector, 1997). It can also be said that employee satisfaction is congenial and sentimental condition, which results from cognizance of allocated work or its practical experience (Locke, 1976). Rainey (1997) says, the satisfaction of employees is extensively read out inconsistent in managerial background on studying employee satisfaction, which is appropriate that how individuals think and perceive their workplace or job and different features of the job. Le'vy-Garboua and Montmarquette (2004) defined employee satisfaction as "a directory of inclination for the practiced career against outside chance provisional on information accessible at time".

An assemble that has often been described, discussed and researched is also known as employee's satisfaction. There are many presumptions concerning the causal relationship between motives, behaviour and proceeds. Employee satisfaction is the measure that tells about the general feeling of an employee about its workplace and job. It measures his attitude towards the job and the degree to which the job is fulfilling the employee's needs. As many researchers concluded that, the satisfaction of employees is used to measure the intentions of an employee towards their workplace (Cranny et al., 1992; Sweeney et al., 2002). Many factors have been determined by the researchers like enthusiastic behavior, hygiene factors, managerial responsibility and workplace environment by building on different theories. (Darrow, 1971; Igalens and Roussel, 1999; Kuo et al., 2007; Brewer et al., 2008; Ahsan et al., 2009).

In literature, a number of practices have been done for the satisfaction of employees. The most important to which is the Maslow's hierarchy of need. In this theory, he suggests that individual needs starts from the basic need (food, cloth and shelter) and ends at the level of self-actualization. Researchers such as Kuhlén (1963) and Conrad et al. (1985), approached to find the factors affecting the satisfaction of employee based on the theory of necessity.

For the success of any business, it is necessary to satisfy the employees. A lower turnover rate is seen among the organizations where the employees are more satisfied. Therefore, satisfaction of employees is the preference of every employer. Whereas this is an ordinary fact in management practices, the downturn in a business comes when the employers ignore satisfaction needs of employees. There are a number of reasons that causes employees to resign an organization; it includes high work responsibilities, low empowerment, low appreciation, limited chance of growth, or limited communication with the supervisor. Managers should keenly observe these factors to decrease the turnover rate, for this, they should monitor the working attitude of their employees, and if they find any element of deprivation in the employees, the employer must address this issue on war basis to improve the working of the employees. . Even in an economic downturn, turnover is an expense best avoided. This study is focuses on that is the employee empowerment has effect on satisfaction of employees. Whether or not workplace environment has any effect on satisfaction of employees? Is there have any effect of pay & promotion on employee satisfaction? How employee satisfaction can affect turnover intention?

Employee satisfaction's definition has been anticipated in literature as multiple theories. For instance, Herzberg's (1968) theory explained that the factors that create satisfaction for an employee are different from the factors that create dissatisfaction. He explained motivators (create satisfaction) and hygiene factors (create dissatisfaction) as the two parts of his theory (Petty et al., 2005).

2.2 Relationship between Empowerment and Employee Satisfaction

Employee empowerment includes that to what extent employees are authorized in decision making in their daily activities. (Carless, 2004; Haas, 2010). Hales and Klidas (1998) define it is the sharing of power and authority with your sub ordinates. Cunningham et al. (1996) defines the empowerment as the downgrading of power for decision making towards the employees without power. Conger and Kanungo (1988) define empowerment as s concept related to motivation and a feeling to improve self-confidence among the employees. Thomas and Velthouse (1990) explained that empowerment cannot be explained in just one manner rather than managerial implementations and feelings of workers should also be considered. As empowerment of the employees very much linked with the techniques and methods of organizations, such as communication, confidence, motivation, employee participation, training and feedback, makes it compulsory to analyze the idea and management direction from various points of view. When the type of authority is checked, it is known that empowerment does capitulate useful result and when the constituents of sub ordinate's authority is checked, it is emphasized that the outcome will generate favourable outcomes for employer as well as for employee (Baruch, 1998). The studies carried out on employee empowerment clearly show that it produces institutional commitment (Sigler and Pearson, 2000; Kim, 2002; Spreitzer; Mishra, 2002 and Han et al., 2009), stimulation (Caudron, 1995; Janssen et al., 1997), performance (C,o'l, 2008; Locke, 1991; Sigler and Pearson, 2000) and client's fulfillment (Bowen and Lawler, 1992; Chebat and Kollias, 2000). The authorization of worker covers an extensive circle of routine activities and the mode the authorization activities are undertaken according to its inside that

were grown, it is linked to satisfaction of employees that they will get. The authority which is taken from isolation, freedom of individual activities, shared administrative and quality of job (Eccles, 1993; Spreitzer et al., 1999b) and is prevalent (Bartunek and Spreitzer, 2006), apprehends a form of employee’s active participation program (Wilkinson, 1998) and encourages the employee to make independent decisions without the advice of their supervisors. Hence, the administrative manners are commenced from the bottom to infuse confidence among the employees (Michailova, 2002). Authorization or empowerment means that employees at any level can perform the leader’s role and must be given freedom to make decisions at their own level about issues concerning their community. While the supervisor must take the seat of the trainer or instructor for a positive change in the organization (Robert et al., 2000) to transform it into a vibrant institution where all levels of supervisors and employees are considered important (Lovell, 1992; Humborstad et al., 2008b). Such practices can stimulate the leading employees to render quality service as an effect to which they are empowered. (Malhotra and Mukherjee, 2003; Hancer and George, 2003).

H1: Empowerment has positive impact on Employee Satisfaction.

2.3 Relationship between Pay & Promotion and Employee Satisfaction

The level of satisfaction is influenced with the level of pay and benefits and promotion system. The company must make policies for the satisfaction of employees to achieve organizational goal. The success of organization greatly indebted to the motivated employees who play an important role in this regard. The employees can be stimulated through enhancement in pay, allowances and promotion. The higher the productivity of the organization, the lower the employee turnover will be. The compensation is defined as the remuneration received by employee from employer against his service. The reward is found as the number one factor of employee satisfaction. The opportunities of promotion in the organization also influence the employee performance. It also increases the performance of employee. The increments granted to the employee in his pay also show that how much this employee is important for organization. An employee should be awarded incentives according to his/her competencies for retention.

The previous practice was to increase the wage rate to enhance satisfaction level and motivate an employee. (Hill &

The quality of physical environmental affects perception, feelings and satisfaction of job (Zalesny et al., 1985; Ferguson and Weisman, 1986; Oldham and Fried, 1987;

Wiens-Tuers 2002). Survey results of Kathawala, Moore and Elmuti (1990) showed that the only factor that influences the motivational and satisfaction level of salaried employees in an automobile industry is the salary package. It is significant to note that reward or compensation is a very important instrument to control employee turnover. It also motivates the organizational commitment of the employee, which in turn attract and retain the employee with the job (Zobal, 1998; Chiu et al., 2002; Moncarz et al., 2009). For an employee, the wages of the co-worker are more important than his own (Cappelli and Sherer 1988, Clark and Oswald 1996, Brown et al 2008, and others). Hammermesh (2001) found that the increment in the earning shocks have noteworthy effect on employee job satisfaction, although its effect is temporary.

H2: Pay & Promotion has a positive impact on employee satisfaction.

2.4 Relationship between Workplace Environment and Employee Satisfaction

Workplace environment includes the location of the work, where the employee performs his duties and daily activities, such as office or site of construction. Generally other factors like, noise level, fresh air, refreshment and the incentives e.g. child care, also become a part of workplace environment. Workplace environment may have either positive or negative impact on the satisfaction level of employees depending upon the nature of working environment. If the environment is good then employee can perform better. The working environment of the organization is directly proportional to the working outcomes; the more it is conducive the better the outcome will be. Employee satisfaction plays an important role in the success of organization. If the physical working environment is good then the employees will perform better. There are various aspects of the physical environment satisfaction that contribute in employee’s satisfaction. Researchers asked the question from the employees that may include that how much you are satisfied with your working environment.

When an employee is given higher level of satisfaction then it reduces turnover and in turn enhances the morale of an employee. (Dole and Schroeder, 2001). Carlopio (1996) found that satisfaction with workplace is positively linked with job fulfillment and it is indirectly linked with organizational commitment and turnovers for better future.

Sundstrom et al., 1994; Carlopio, 1996; Leather et al., 2003; Lee and Brand, 2005).

The current workplace environment of various organizations has positive association with satisfaction of employees.

H3: Satisfaction with the workplace environment has positive impact on Employee Satisfaction.

2.5 Relationship between Employee Satisfaction and Turnover Intention

To accomplish the study objectives, the turnover intention is considered to be as leaving the company or department (Tett & Meyer, 1993). Those people who have studied before for the betterment of behavioral meaning literature (Ajzen and Fishben 1975) developed a beautiful model that identifies the best reasonable translator of the individual behavior to be reported and evaluated. Intention to perform that behaviour although highlighting turnover a basic element in the specimen of employees' income. According to some scholars, personal behavior is the single best predictor of turnover. (Michaels & Spector, 1982; Lee & Mowday, 1987; Abrams, Ando, & Hinkle, 1998).

Satisfaction of employees shows a negative relationship with the employee turnover intention (Muchinsky & Mor-

row, 1980; Trevor, 2001). When the employees are pleased with their job then there is low level of leaving the organization and when the employee is not given his rights when he is not satisfied with the job then there is intention of the employee to discontinue the job.

As said by Trevor (2001), the model that was developed by March and Simon (1958), results in voluntary turnover models. As practically suggested and chances for productivity, the researchers studied the employee turnover intention many times over the period in a number of areas of research, sometimes the researchers examined the employee turnover intention as negative relationship to employee job satisfaction (Gerhart, Boudreau, Sturman & Trevor, 2003).

H4: Employee satisfaction has negative impact on turnover intention.

2.6 Proposed Model of the Research

According to the given research hypothesis a model is developed which is as under:

Figure 1. Proposed Model

3. Research Methodology

The current research is descriptive in nature. Descriptive research can be explained as describing something, some phenomenon or any particular situation. Descriptive researches are those researches that describe the existing situation instead of interpreting and making judgments (Creswell, 1994). The main objective of the descriptive research is verification of the developed hypothesis that reflects the current situation. This type of research provides information about the current scenario and focus on past and present, e.g. quality of life in a community or customer attitudes towards any marketing activity (Kumar, 2005).

3.1 Sample/Data

In order to collect the data for understanding the employee satisfaction level in various organizations. A sample of 150 respondents will ask to participate in a self-administered questionnaire. The population for the current research is the employees from public sector and private sector organizations. The current study utilizes a non-probability sampling technique that is convenience sampling. Convenience sampling is sampling technique that obtains and collects the relevant information from sample or the unit of study that are conveniently available (Zikmund, 1997).

It has ensured that the sample members possess different qualification and different scale of jobs to participate in the self-administered survey. The sample member should be employees of organization; this identifies their satisfaction level with their job and turnover intention among them. We select these sample members from different organizations of

Bahawalpur City (Punjab, Pakistan). Two main clusters were targeted to collect the sample data university employees and some private organizations in the city.

3.2 Instrument and Scales

The survey instrument of the current study addresses two major purposes; first is to analyze the relationship of different variables in employee satisfaction, second to collect information about the different characteristics of the respondents that can be used to understand the variations in different categories.

The survey instrument contains two sections; section one includes different personal and demographic variables. This section will obtain the respondents information about gender, age, income and education. Section 2 includes the latent variables that are important in the current study. These variables include employee empowerment, pay & promotion, workplace environment, employee satisfaction and turnover intention. This section of the study is developed based on the past literature and already used questionnaires.

The scales of the study were adopted from the previous literature and published studies. The first three variables of the study were employee empowerment, pay & promotion and workplace environment. The items of these variables were taken from the researches of Hayes 1994, Kabir & Parvin 2011 and Lee 2006 respectively. The next variable is employee satisfaction having three items taken from Hackman and Oldham, 1975 and the last variable is turnover intention having four items taken from Seashore et al., 1982.

Variables	Items	Reference
Employee Empowerment (EE)	I have the authority to correct customer problems when they occur.	Hayes, 1994
	I am encouraged to handle customer problems by myself.	
	I do not have to get management's approval before I handle customer problems.	
	I am allowed to do almost anything to solve customer problems.	
	I have control over how I solve customer problems.	
Pay & Promotion (PP)	I am satisfied with the existing salary structure of the company	Parvin & Kabir, 2011
	I am satisfied with the compensation I get and I think it matches with my responsibility.	
Workplace Environment (WPE)	My workplace provides an undisturbed environment so that I can concentrate on my work.	Lee, 2006
	My furniture is flexible enough to adjust, rearrange, or reorganize my workspace.	
	The quality of my equipment is more than sufficient to work effectively.	
	I am able to control temperature or airflow in my office.	
	I am able to determine the organization/appearance of my work area.	
	I am able to be easily accessed from my colleague's workstation.	
	My workstation is over-equipped for my typical needs.	
	I am able to control the lighting level in my workstation.	
Employee Satisfaction (ES)	You are satisfied with your job currently.	Hackman and Oldham, 1975
	Your work environment is pleasant.	
	You are extremely glad that you chose this company to work for, over other organizations.	
Turnover Intention (TI)	You are very likely to stay in this company for the next five years.	Seashore et al., 1982
	For you, this company is the best of all possible organizations to work for.	
	You will not give up this company easily.	
	You seldom hear about or are exposed to jobs outside your company that interest you.	

3.3 Procedure

The questionnaire was distributed among 200 respondents in Bahawalpur City before giving the questionnaire. The pur-

pose of study and questions were explained to the respondents so they can easily fill the questionnaire with relevant responses. 150 questionnaires were selected and rests of the

questionnaires were not included in the further analysis due to incomplete or invalid responses. After collecting the completed questionnaires, these questionnaires were coded and entered into SPSS sheet for further regression analysis.

3.4 Reliability Analysis

Overall cronbachs alphas of all variables in our study are more than acceptable and recommended value 0.50 by Nunnally (1970) and 0.60 by Moss et al. (1998). This shows that all the 22 items were reliable and valid to measure the opinion of employees towards their satisfaction.

Table 2: Reliability Analysis

Scales	Items	Cronbach alpha
Employee Empowerment	5	0.831
Pay & Promotion	2	0.797
Workplace Environment	8	0.809
Employee Satisfaction	3	0.686
Turnover Intention	4	0.713

4. Results and Analysis

4.1 Profile OF the Respondents

Personal and demographic information includes gender, age, income and education level are presented in the following table.

Table 3: Profile of the respondents

	Categories	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	120	80.0
	Female	30	20.0
	Total	150	100.0
Age	below 18	1	.7
	18-25	38	25.3
	25-35	51	34.0
	35-45	35	23.3
	45 and above	25	16.7
	Total	150	100.0
Education Level	Metric	10	6.7
	Intermediate	14	9.3
	Graduation	44	29.3
	Master	75	50.0
	M.Phil/Phd	7	4.7
	Total	150	100.0
Income Level	below 15000	27	18.0
	15001-30000	55	36.7
	30001-45000	40	26.7
	45001 and above	26	17.3
	5	2	1.3
	Total	150	100.0

4.2 Hypothesis Testing

4.2.1 Employee Empowerment & Employee Satisfaction

According to the result of the study employee empowerment (EE) has a significant positive association with employee satisfaction (ES) with $\beta = 0.274$ and $P < 0.01$ that means the EE contributes to more than 27% to ES.

4.2.2 Pay & Promotion & Employee Satisfaction

According to the result of the study, Pay & Promotion (PP) has a negative relationship with ES with $\beta = 0.039$ and $P > 0.01$ that means the PP contributes to less than 1% to ES.

4.2.3 Workplace Environment & Employee Satisfaction

According to the result of the study workplace environment (WPE) has a significant positive association with ES with $\beta = 0.427$ and $P < 0.01$ that means the WPE contributes to more than 42% to ES.

4.2.4 Employee Satisfaction & Turnover Intention

According to the result of the study employee satisfaction (ES) has a significant negative relationship with Turnover Intention (TI) with $\beta = 0.577$ and $P < 0.01$ that means the ES contributes to more than 27% to TI.

Table 4: Regression Results

Hypothesis	Model Variables	Estimates	S.E.	C.R.	P	Results
H1	ES ↑ EE	0.274	0.065	3.675	0.000	supported
H2	ES ↑ PP	0.039	0.048	-0.577	0.565	not supported
H3	ES ↑ WPE	0.427	0.80	5.810	0.000	supported
H4	TI ↑ ES	-0.577	0.64	-8.605	0.000	supported

Figure 2. Regression Results of the Model

5. DISCUSSION

This research has been conducted in the private sector as well as in public sector organizations of Bahawalpur City. The main objective of this research is to know the antecedents that have effect on employee satisfaction in any organization. We analyze many of past researches and choose the variables from that research papers to find their effect on the organizations in Bahawalpur City. This research also ensures that is there any correlation in employee satisfaction and employee turnover intention?

We conducted this research by taking the sample of 200 employees from target population. 150 of the employees responded to our questionnaire. Our research consists of two parts, in the first part, we use employee empowerment, pay

and promotion and workplace environment as independent variables and employee satisfaction as a dependent variable. In the second part, we took employee satisfaction as independent variable and turnover intention as a dependent variable. We conducted analysis on the data collected from the samples. The results show that EE has a significant positive relationship and it contributes more than 27% to ES. Therefore, when an employee is given autonomy in business decisions then his satisfaction level will rise. Similarly, PP has a negative relation with ES and it contributes less than 1% to ES. As it has a negative impact on employee satisfaction, it means that besides pay and promotion there are other more influential factors on employee satisfaction.

$\beta = -0.577$ $R^2 = 0.329$
H4

Our next variable is workplace environment, according to the result of the study WPE has noteworthy positive relationship ES contributing more than 42% to ES. It shows that when an employee is given favorable and clean environment then its satisfaction level rises.

In the second part of our research, paper we analyze the relationship between employee satisfaction and employee turnover intentions means intention towards leaving the organization. Whenever there is low level of employee satisfaction in any organization, the employees of that organization will intentionally leave that organization. According to the result of the study, ES has a significant negative relationship with TI contributing more than 27% to TI.

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